

INFERRING QUANTITATIVE TYPOLOGICAL TRENDS FROM MULTILINGUAL TREEBANKS. A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT: In the past decades, linguistic typology went through a renewing phase that involved a significant change in the research questions and methods of the discipline, which is now interested in fine-grained features underlying language diversity. In this paper, we propose a novel approach to address the newly defined needs of linguistic typology by extracting qualitative and quantitative information about a wide range of features from multilingual annotated corpora based on Natural Language Processing methods and techniques. We tested our method in a case study focusing on word order variation in two widely investigated constructions, VERB-SUBJ(ect) and NOUN-ADJ(ective), with a specific view to structural and functional factors underlying the preference for one or the other order, both intra- and cross-linguistically, and their interaction. Preliminary experiments have been carried out aimed at acquiring typological evidence from a selection of linguistically annotated treebanks for three different languages, namely Italian, Spanish and English. Our results show the effectiveness of the method in letting similarities and differences also emerge from typologically close languages.

KEYWORDS: Language Typology, Multilingual Annotated Corpora, Linguistic Knowledge Extraction and Modelling, Word Order Variation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, linguistic typology shifted its focus from the quest for universals to the study of the distribution of the features underlying linguistic diversity. As claimed by Bickel (2007), typology has recently reached

a new stage of its life: the discipline has passed from determining what is possible, as opposed to impossible, in human language, to developing theories aimed at explaining language diversity. This new paradigm profoundly shook the discipline foundations, in terms of both research questions and methodology, and brought to the development of what is now called “Distributional Typology” (DT, Bickel, 2015).

Distributional Typology is a general framework for comparative linguistics that applies statistical methods to large sets of fine-grained variables (rather than “grand type notions”, Bickel, 2007) corresponding to individual structures (e.g. constructions, relations, distinctive features, orderings, etc.) characterizing each language in order to determine the factors driving the distribution of linguistic patterns over time and space.

The information sources at the basis of the studies in DT are typological linguistic databases, such as the “World Atlas of Language Structures” (WALS, Dryer and Haspelmath, 2013), which contain information pertaining to one or several levels of linguistic description for many languages. Despite the high number and variety of linguistic structures documented in typological databases, this type of resource has two main shortcomings concerning the coverage and the discrete nature of features (Ponti et al., 2019). If on the one hand they present gaps in attributes and missing values (e.g. WALS currently covers about 17% of its possible feature values), on the other hand - and most importantly for our purposes here - they fail to account for variation within a single language: only possible or the most frequent (“dominant” in WALS terms) values are reported, without associated probabilities of occurrence. This follows from the fact that information in typological databases is manually encoded, mostly derived from secondary sources such as grammars, dictionaries and scientific papers.

An alternative or integrative knowledge source with respect to typological databases is represented by corpora testifying real language usage, such as linguistically annotated treebanks, from which quantitative typological trends can be inferred, highlighting shared and distinctive properties of languages (among treebank-based studies see e.g. Liu (2010), Futrell et al. (2015), Gulordava and Merlo (2015a;2015b), Gulordava (2018), Sharma et al. (2019)).

Nowadays, the growing availability of linguistically annotated corpora for many languages combined with the increasing reliability of Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods and tools enables the acquisition of quantitative evidence which can significantly contribute to the investigation of the issues opened by Distributional Typology. Interestingly, this line of research is also becoming a hot topic within the NLP community, since linguistic typology is seen to hold promise to support new solutions towards the development of

robust and multilingually applicable NLP technologies and tools. In fact, typological information has recently started to be integrated in multilingual NLP algorithms and applications to provide guidance and improve processing accuracy (see Ponti et al., 2019 for a complete survey).

In this paper, we propose a novel methodology which aims at meeting the newly defined needs of linguistic typology by extracting quantitative information about a wide range of fine-grained features from multilingual annotated corpora. The method has been tested in a case study focusing on word order variation, a topic which has always received a lot of attention in typological studies (see, among many others, Cristofaro, 2018; Dryer, 1992, 2009; Greenberg, 1963; Hawkins, 1983, 1994; Payne, 1992; Siewierska, 1988; Song, 2010). Preliminary experiments have been carried out aimed at acquiring quantitative typological evidence from a selection of linguistically annotated treebanks for different languages, with the specific goal of reconstructing word order patterns (defined in terms of both linear order of words and degree of flexibility) within and across languages. For the acquired word order patterns, the study also aims at investigating the factors underlying the preference for one or the other order, both intra- and cross-linguistically. These experiments have been carried out on three typologically and geographically close languages, namely Italian, Spanish and English, sharing the classical typological classification as Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) languages (Dryer, 2013). We believe that assessing the method with typologically close languages is challenging: its effectiveness in letting similarities and differences emerge from them is not to be taken for granted.

With this case study, we aim at showing to linguists and in particular to typologists the potential of the proposed NLP-based method in providing relevant insights for typological studies and in possibly opening new lines of research in the area. Given the scenario depicted above, the basic research questions we intend to investigate here are:

- **RQ1:** from a methodological point of view, whether and to what extent NLP-based methods and techniques applied to linguistically annotated multilingual corpora can provide novel evidence to feed Distributional Typology studies;
- **RQ2:** from a linguistic point of view, what are the word order patterns characterizing each language, what are the factors underlying them and determining their variation intra-linguistically, how similarities and differences across languages can be detected and measured.

2. RELATED LITERATURE

Corpus-based studies can help to automatically acquire quantitative typological evidence useful to model linguistic variation within and across languages. In recent trends of linguistic typology, distributional and statistical methods are used to acquire information about what makes languages behave similarly or differently (Bickel, 2007; Nichols, 2007; Song, 2010). This information can also be used to enrich typological databases with complex and articulated frequency distributions of language constructions.

Corpora annotated with morpho-syntactic and syntactic information, i.e. treebanks, are exploited to obtain and quantify large-scale evidence of properties shared by many languages such as Dependency Length Minimization (DLM). The case of this largely documented universal property (Gibson, 1998; Hawkins, 1994; Demberg and Keller, 2008; Temperley, 2007) effectively proves the benefits of acquiring linguistic information from corpora: the availability of 37 hand-corrected treebanks allowed Futrell et al. (2015a) to empirically show that dependency length is actually minimized in real utterances across many languages and language families.

Multilingual annotated corpora have also been used to investigate cross-linguistic similarities and differences. Word order variation represents one of the most widely investigated topics from this perspective. In this case, available treebanks provide essential language samples to carry out extensive studies on the degree of word order freedom across languages or the language tendency to head-initial or head-final word orders. This is the case, for instance, of Futrell et al. (2015b) who proposed novel measures for quantifying word order freedom using recently available dependency corpora for 34 languages, or Liu (2010) who analyzed treebanks representative of 20 different languages to study dependency direction tendencies.

Besides allowing large-scale investigations on word order properties, typological studies carried out on annotated corpora can also help identifying factors underlying word order alternation between languages. An example is represented by Gulordava and Merlo (2015a)'s study, where the authors looked at structural (e.g. heaviness effect, DLM) and lexical (e.g. collocations) factors that play a role in adjective-noun word order alternations in Romance languages. Annotated corpora can also be used to study diachronic evolution of word order such as differences occurring between older Latin, and Ancient Greek texts, and modern Romance languages, and modern Greek, as reported by Gulordava and Merlo (2015b), who demonstrated that ancient languages exhibit longer dependencies and freer word order than modern texts.

The shift of focus in typological studies towards the distribution of features underlying linguistic diversity recently started to contribute to open a

fruitful reflection in the NLP community on how typological information can provide useful guidance for the development of multilingual NLP algorithms. As claimed by Ponti et al. (2018): “Understanding linguistic variation in a systematic way is crucial for the development of effective multilingual NLP applications, thus making NLP technology more accessible globally”. Research questions in this direction concern the design of computational methods to obtain typological information that can combine a discrete representation of language features, such as the one contained in typological databases, with a continuous one learned adopting NLP-based approaches to language modelling (Dunn et al. 2011; Cotterell and Eisner 2017; Bjerva and Augenstein 2018; Bjerva et al., 2019).

This new trend of typological studies has also been prompted by the availability of the multi-lingual treebanks developed within the Universal Dependencies project¹ for over 50 languages. Universal Dependencies (UD) is a framework for cross-linguistically consistent treebank annotation aiming to capture similarities as well as idiosyncrasies among typologically different languages (e.g., morphologically rich languages, pro-drop languages, and languages featuring clitic doubling). The goal in developing UD was not only to support comparative evaluation and cross-lingual parsing but also to enable comparative linguistic studies (Nivre, 2015). Corpora annotated with the same inventory of dependency relations and sharing annotation guidelines are paving the way toward methods able to track and quantify linguistic variation across languages avoiding possible interferences due to multiple annotation schemata. They made it possible, for example, to classify languages according to structural parameters such as dependency direction (Chen and Gerdes, 2017) and word order (Sharma et al., 2019), or to compare treebanks with respect to the Dependency Length Minimization (Yu et al., 2019).

3. THE PROBLEM

Let us introduce the topic of this paper by looking at how typological databases report information about the relative ordering of constituents at both clausal and phrasal levels. In this study, we focus on the VERB-SUBJ(ect) and NOUN-ADJ(ective) constructions as representative of the clausal and phrasal levels respectively.

Table 1 reports - for the three languages considered in this study - the different orderings of lexical (i.e. non pronominal) Subject and Verb, and of

¹ <http://universaldependencies.org/>

Adjective and Noun as resulting from the “World Atlas of Language Structures” (WALS) and the “Syntactic Structures of the World’s Languages” (SSWL)² databases. It can be noted that the two provide a slightly different picture for the three languages, following from the fact that whereas WALS records the “dominant” order, SSWL testifies “productive” word order patterns. According to WALS, no dominant VERB-SUBJ order exists for both Italian and Spanish (Dryer, 2013a), whereas Subject-Verb is considered a productive word order for both of them in SSWL. If Adjective-Noun is a productive order for all three languages according to SSWL, in WALS the Noun-Adjective order is considered dominant in Italian and Spanish, while the reverse order is reported as dominant for English (Dryer, 2013b).

WALS				
CONSTRUCTION	WORD ORDER	ENGLISH	ITALIAN	SPANISH
VERB-SUBJ	Subject-Verb	+	No dominant order	No dominant order
	Verb-Subject	-	No dominant order	No dominant order
NOUN-ADJ	Adjective-Noun	+	-	-
	Noun-Adjective	-	+	+
SSWL				
VERB-SUBJ	Subject-Verb	+	+	+
	Verb-Subject	-	+	+
NOUN-ADJ	Adjective-Noun	+	+	+
	Noun-Adjective	+	+	+

TABLE 1. WORD ORDERING PATTERNS OF VERB-SUBJ AND NOUN-ADJ CONSTRUCTIONS ATTESTED IN WALS AND SSWL DATABASES FOR THE SELECTED LANGUAGES.

This partly contradictory picture can be refined and unified if we take into account actual frequencies of occurrence extracted from corpora. Consider the picture emerging from the English, Italian and Spanish UD treebanks. Table 2 reports, for the three treebanks, the percentage distribution of different word

² <http://sswl.railsplayground.net/>

orders involving lexical (i.e. non-pronominal) Subjects and Verbs, and Adjectives and Nouns respectively. The three languages turned out to prefer the Subject-Verb order, but with significant differences: namely, the Italian and Spanish treebanks are characterized by a much higher percentage of left-headed subjects (22.38% and 16.94% respectively) than English (where they only represent 3.58% of the cases). For what concerns adjectival modifiers, whereas for English the Adjective-Noun order is highly preferred, in Italian and Spanish the reverse order (with the adjective occurring on the right side of the head) is the most frequent one. Nonetheless, the Adjective-Noun ordering covers 30.61% and 27.82% of the cases respectively.

UD TREEBANKS				
CONSTRUCTION	WORD ORDER	ENGLISH	ITALIAN	SPANISH
VERB-SUBJ	Subject-Verb	96.42%	77.62%	83.06%
	Verb-Subject	3.58%	22.38%	16.94%
NOUN-ADJ	Adjective-Noun	96.80%	30.61%	27.82%
	Noun-Adjective	3.20%	69.39%	72.18%

TABLE 2. PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF RIGHT- VS LEFT-HEADED NON- PRONOMINAL NSUBJ AND AMOD RELATIONS IN THE THREE UD TREEBANKS.

Thanks to the evidence acquired from corpora, we have seen that different word orders coexist in the same language and that probabilities can be assigned to them. This means that the typological classification of languages on the basis of word order properties is more a matter of degree than of discrete types: in the three languages taken into account, different degrees of flexibility are observed in the internal ordering of elements within VERB-SUBJ and NOUN-ADJ constructions.

In the literature, over the last 10 years there have been quantitative studies on word order variation within and across languages which were made possible thanks to the availability of linguistically annotated corpora. Among them, it is worth mentioning Liu (2010), Chen and Gerdes (2017) and Guzmán Naranjo and Becker (2018), who proposed innovative quantitative methods to investigate word ordering properties of languages based on dependency treebanks for different languages, with the specific aim of capturing cross-linguistic similarities and differences.

These studies demonstrate that frequency information on word ordering properties of languages can be usefully exploited to typologically classify languages. However, the question which immediately arises is whether frequency

alone is sufficient or whether additional parameters are needed to account for the distribution of word ordering patterns. Besides dependency direction and frequency, Liu and Xu (2012), Gulordava and Merlo (2015b) and Chen and Gerdes (2017) also took into account other properties such as “Directional Dependency Distance” (combining dependency distance and direction) or “Head-Dependent Adjacency” (representing a more sensitive free word order measure taking into account adjacency to the head) with interesting results. More recently, Gulordava (2018) provided an insightful analysis on the interaction of word order variation and dependency length minimization.

In all these studies, these properties are analysed individually. In what follows, we will investigate word ordering patterns intra- and cross-linguistically by simultaneously taking into account a wide range of factors also including contextual properties of dependency relations.

4. DATA AND METHOD

Two are the main ingredients of this study, namely linguistically annotated multilingual corpora and a language modelling algorithm which will be used to qualitatively and quantitatively assess the variation observed for the same linguistic construction intra- and cross-linguistically.

FIGURE 1. METHOD WORKFLOW.

A broad picture of the proposed methodology is provided in Figure 1, which visually describes the workflow devised for acquiring typological knowledge from multilingual treebanks. For each language, a large Reference Corpus of automatically dependency parsed sentences is used by a language

modelling algorithm named LISCA (Dell’Orletta et al., 2013) to obtain a language model of the corpus, the LISCA-LM: using a recurrent metaphor of the linguistic literature originally introduced by Jakobson (1973), we can look at the LISCA-LM as encoding the DNA of the language being analysed. The LISCA-LM is then used to assign a score to each Dependency Relation (DR) instance in a manually validated (or “gold”) treebank, which represents the Target Corpus. DRs in the target corpus are then ranked by decreasing LISCA scores: the ranked list of relations represents the starting point of different types of analyses aimed at inferring cross-lingual similarities and differences and identifying quantitative typological trends.

4.1 Corpus Data

Automatic learning of typological information is typically carried out from parallel texts, e.g. through multilingual word alignments (Mayer and Cysouw, 2012; Östling, 2015) or from Interlinear Glossed Texts (Lewis and Xia; 2008; Bender et al., 2013). In this case study, parallelism is not concerned with texts: comparability is guaranteed here by *i*) the same inventory of DRs and annotation guidelines shared by the reference and target multilingual treebanks, and *ii*) the same typology of documents used to build LISCA-LMs. For the specific concerns of this study, we focused on Italian, Spanish and English. As illustrated above, for each language two linguistically annotated corpora have been used: namely, an automatically annotated big Reference Corpus used for building the LISCA-LM and a “gold” Target Corpus with manually revised linguistic annotation used as a source for acquiring quantitative typological information. Note that the combination of two types of textual resources is a key feature of our approach for the acquisition of typological information from corpora: on the one hand the wide coverage corpus permits to quantify statistical trends accounting for different degrees of prototypicality of linguistic structures, on the other hand a highly reliable small Target Corpus guarantees the extraction of linguistically sound results.

The reference corpora used to collect the statistics to build the LISCA-LMs represent a portion of the English, Italian and Spanish Wikipedia, for a total of around 40 million tokens for each language. The corpora were morpho-syntactically annotated and dependency parsed by the UDPipe pipeline (Straka et al., 2016) trained on the Universal Dependency treebanks, version 2.3 (Nivre et al., 2017). The reliability of the language models built on the basis of reference corpora is guaranteed by the size of the selected set of examples, large enough to reflect the actual distribution of phenomena in languages and, at the same time, sufficient to mitigate the effects of the presence of random parsing errors unavoidably occurring in automatically parsed corpora.

The LISCA-LM obtained from each Reference Corpus was then applied to “gold” treebanks. In particular, we used as Target Corpora the Italian, English and Spanish manually validated (or “gold”) Universal Dependencies treebanks:

- the English Web Treebank (Silveira et al., 2014), which contains 254,830 words and 16,622 sentences, taken from five genres of web media: weblogs, newsgroups, emails, reviews, and question and answers;
- the ISDT (“Italian Stanford Dependency Treebank”) section of the Italian Universal Dependency Treebank (Bosco et al., 2013), which contains 14,167 sentences for a total of 278,429 tokens from the news domain;
- the Spanish AnCora UD treebank (Alonso and Zeman, 2016) containing 17,680 sentences and 547,680 tokens from the news domain.

In this case study, we used the UD treebanks released in November 2018, version 2.3.

4.2 The LISCA Algorithm

As represented in Figure 1, LISCA is a language modelling algorithm able to obtain a Language Model (LM) from a large Reference Corpus representative of a given language. The algorithm operates in two steps:

1. it creates the language-specific LISCA-LM_{lang_x} by collecting statistics about a wide set of linguistically motivated features extracted from the Reference Corpus linguistically annotated through automatic dependency parsing;
2. it uses the LISCA-LM_{lang_x} built during the previous step to assign a score to each instance of dependency relation contained in a Target Corpus.

Figure 2 illustrates the features taken into account by LISCA for constructing the LM on the basis of the Reference Corpus. Each DR is defined as a triple (d, h, t) where d is the dependent, h is the head, and t is the type of dependency connecting d to h . In particular, for each DR instance two different types of features are considered:

- *local* features, e.g. the distance in terms of tokens between d and h , or the associative strength linking the grammatical categories involved in the relation (i.e. POS _{d} and POS _{h}), or the POS of the head governor and the type of dependency connecting d to h , or the relative linear order of d and h in the sentence;
- *global* features, aimed at locating each DR instance within the overall syntactic structure of the sentence: for example, the distance of d from the root of the dependency tree, or from the closest or most distant leaf node, or the number of “brothers” and “children” nodes of d , occurring respectively to its right or left in the linear order of the sentence.

FIGURE 2. FEATURES USED BY LISCA.

For the purposes of the present study, LISCA has been used in its de-lexicalized version in order to abstract away from variation resulting from lexical effects and thus guaranteeing cross-lingual comparability of results.

To exemplify LISCA working principles, consider, for example, the different Italian subject relation instances (*nsubj* in UD parlance) reported in Figure 3. The subjects in *a*) (lit.³ ‘In this case, he *is-responsible* within the limits ...’) and *c*) (lit. ‘... the *rights* not overtly granted by the Licensor remain confidential’) occur in pre-verbal position. There are however important differences worth noting here: in *a*) a pronominal subject immediately precedes the verb, while in *c*) a long-distance DR (whose length is equal to 7) links the lexical subject to its head. On the other hand, the sentence in *b*) (lit. ‘Here, from each corner of the world, arrive 300 thousand *patients*’) exemplifies a lexical post-verbal subject.

³ In the translation of examples, the dependent is italicized and the head underlined.

FIGURE 3. NSUBJ INSTANCES RANKED BY DECREASING LISCA SCORES.

In Figure 3, examples *a)*, *b)* and *c)* are ranked by decreasing LISCA scores. The LISCA score reflects the probability to observe a relation in a given context on the basis of the Language Model constructed starting from the Reference Corpus. Note that several factors of different nature (both local and global ones) are taken into account in the definition of the context of occurrence of a DR instance, which thus contribute to its scoring. If we compare the LISCA ranking of relations in Figure 3 with the frequency distribution of the Subject-Verb and Verb-Subject orders reported in Table 2 for Italian, it can be noted that the LISCA ranking of *nsubj* instances is not aligned with the frequency distribution of the different types of orders. In fact, on the basis of this, examples in *a)* and *c)* should be seen as more likely VERB-SUBJECT instances than *b)*. Instead, LISCA on the basis of the local and global properties taken into account assigned *a)* a higher score than *b)*, whose score is in turn higher than that assigned to *c)*. Note that the LISCA-LM is de-lexicalized, hence it is not sensitive to the fact that *arrivare* ‘arrive’ is an unaccusative verb whose subject typically occurs in post-verbal position. From the resulting LISCA ranking of *nsubj* relations, it turned out that in Italian longer distance subjects are less prototypical (or “marked”, see below) than post-verbal adjacent ones; it is also likely that the grammatical category of the subject (pronoun vs noun) plays a role in defining the LISCA score. This shows that LISCA is able to account for a complex mix of interacting factors, both structural and functional, which also include processing biases (cfr. the score assigned by LISCA to the long-distance pre-verbal subject in example *c)* of Figure 3).

The ranking of the examples in Figure 3 demonstrates that the LISCA score results from the interaction of several factors, concerning both structural and functional characteristics: in other words, the LISCA scores reflect the degree of similarity of the “linguistic environments” in which a given DR occurs in the Reference and Target corpora. The question which naturally arises at this point concerns the linguistic interpretation of the score and in particular of the

resulting ranking of relations. Following Tusa et al. (2016), the LISCA score is interpreted here as reflecting the “markedness” degree of a specific linguistic structure: whereas higher scores are assigned to “unmarked” (i.e. more frequent and likely) constructions, lower scores are associated with less usual or less expected, i.e. “marked”, constructions. From this it follows that the ranked list of DRs by decreasing LISCA scores reflects, for a given DR type, the transition from unmarked prototypical relation instances to highly marked ones. Haspelmath (2006) discusses 12 different senses of the widely debated “markedness” notion: among them, we refer here to “Markedness as Abnormality”, and in particular to *Markedness as rarity in texts* and *Markedness as restricted distribution*. The LISCA score reflects both these micro-facets of the notion: on the one hand, the frequency of occurrence in actual language use, and on the other hand the occurrence in specific contexts. The LISCA ranking of DRs of a given treebank can thus be used to infer quantitative evidence about the gradual transition from unmarked (or prototypical) to marked (or less canonical) DR instances, given the relative ordering of *h* and *d*, their associated grammatical categories, their distance in terms of tokens as well as the context of occurrence of *t* defined through both local and global features.

4.3 Two Types of Analysis of the LISCA Ranking of DRs

The LISCA ranking of dependencies obtained for each UD treebank on the basis of a language-specific LISCA-LM_{lang_x} has been investigated from a two-fold perspective, namely *multilingual* and *cross-lingual*, with the final goal of acquiring quantitative typological evidence for what concerns word order patterns.

In the *multilingual* analysis, the ranked lists of DRs obtained for each treebank are compared to detect and measure similarities and differences across languages. This comparison focuses on specific DRs: for each language, the distribution of the different instances of a given DR (described in terms of the associated local and global features) in the ranked list of treebank relations is extracted and quantified. We start from the assumption that the position of a given DR instance in the language-specific ranking reflects its degree of markedness from a monolingual perspective: the higher the position, the more prototypical and less marked the DR instance is for that language. By comparing the rankings obtained for a given DR type within each language, it is possible to capture and measure similarities and differences across languages with respect to individual structures, represented here in terms of contextualized dependency relations. To be more concrete, languages which differ for the typical (or dominant in WALS terms) pre- or post-nominal position of the modifying adjective will rank differently the Noun-Adj and Adj-Noun sequences:

e.g. in languages with dominant pre-nominal adjectives the Adj-Noun sequence will be ranked highly in the LISCA ranking, whereas the reverse will occur with the Noun-Adj ordering.

In principle, however, differences detected by comparing the distribution of DRs in the ranked list of relations of different treebanks could also originate from genre-specific, rather than language-specific, peculiarities. This is one of the major disadvantages seen by typologists as connected with the use of corpus evidence in typological studies (see e.g. Roland, 2007; Liu, 2008; Liu, 2010). As reported in Section 4.1, the treebanks taken into account in this case study differ at the level of their internal composition: they do not contain documents representative of the same textual genres, a fact which can have consequences also at the level of linguistic annotation (Plank, 2016).

To overcome the potential interferences due to the corpus composition, another type of analysis is proposed here, henceforth referred to as *cross-lingual* analysis. In this type of analysis, for the same monolingual treebank three DR rankings are obtained, each resulting from the application of a language-specific LISCA-LM_{lang_x}. The underlying intuition is that different positions of the same DR instance across the three rankings are connected with typological similarities and/or differences of the considered languages: a bigger ranking difference associated with the same DR instance is connected with stronger typological differences of the languages analysed, whereas closer ranking reflects typological closeness of languages. In other words, by looking at a given language through the glasses of the LISCA-LM developed for another language helps highlighting and quantifying the features motivating typological (un)relatedness of the two languages.

Figure 4 visually exemplifies this type of analysis. For instance, the post-nominal adjectival modifier (*amod*) extracted from the ISDT section of the Italian UD Treebank occurring in the 90,776th position of the ranking obtained using the Italian model (hereafter LISCA-LM_{Ita}) moved down to the 141,385th one in the ranking obtained using the English model (LISCA-LM_{Eng}) and up to the 90,139th position in the ranking obtained using the Spanish model (LISCA-LM_{Esp}).

FIGURE 4. CROSS-LINGUAL ANALYSIS MODEL.

Looking at post-nominal adjectives (the most likely ones in Italian) through the glasses of a language characterized by the reverse order such as English explains why LISCA assigned a lower score to the same DR ranked using the LISCA-LM_{Eng}. On the contrary, with a typologically similar language like Spanish, the ranking positions are much closer.

5. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results obtained with the multilingual and cross-lingual analysis approaches described above are reported in the following. To demonstrate the potential of this methodology of analysis, we focused on two widely investigated constructions in the typological literature on word ordering, i.e. nominal subject (encoded as *nsubj* in the UD annotation scheme) and adjectival modifier (in UD, *amod*).

5.1 Multilingual Analysis Results

In the multilingual analysis approach, similarities and differences among languages are captured by comparing the distribution of DRs within each language-specific ranking: this distribution is taken to reflect different degrees of markedness of the different DR instances. To facilitate the comparison of DR distributions, each ranked list of DRs has been subdivided into 10 groups, henceforth “bins”, each corresponding to 10% of the total. For a matter of clarity, we consider bins 1 to 3 as roughly corresponding to the head of the ranking, bins 4 to 7 as middle, 8-10 as the tail.

5.1.1 Multilingual distribution of adjectival modifiers and nominal subjects

Let us first consider the distribution of adjectival modifiers and nominal subjects across the bins of the LISCA rankings of the Italian, Spanish and English treebanks, abstracting away from the relative ordering of head and dependent. As illustrated in Figure 5, both DRs show language specific peculiarities, as reflected by their distributions.

FIGURE 5. DISTRIBUTION ACROSS THE LISCA BINS OF NSUBJ AND AMOD DRs IN ITALIAN, SPANISH AND ENGLISH.

For what concerns nominal subjects, Figure 5 reports the distribution of lexical subjects only: whereas English *nsubj* DRs appear in the head of the LISCA ranking, the first occurrences of *nsubj* DRs for Italian and Spanish occur in the middle part of the ranking. In general, Italian and Spanish distributions share a similar trend, reflecting the higher similarity of the two Romance languages if compared to English: while in English *nsubj* DRs appear in the head of the ranking and show a descending trend moving towards the tail, Italian and Spanish concentrate the majority of *nsubj* DRs in the tail of their rankings. Different factors seem to contribute to this distribution. Among them frequency plays a key role. Whereas Italian and Spanish are pro-drop languages, English obligatorily requires an explicit subject: this implies that the overall number of overt subjects (both lexical and pronominal) corresponds to 8.60% of all relations in the treebank for English and only to 4.95% and 5.40% in Italian and Spanish (since null subjects are not explicitly marked in the UD annotation scheme). However, it is interesting to report that other

factors come into play here. Differently from lexical subjects, pronominal subjects show a similar distribution in all languages, i.e. they appear earlier (2nd, 3rd and 4th bins in English, Spanish and Italian respectively), mainly concentrate in the first half of the bins and show a similar descending distribution in the tail. In spite of this, they show quite different frequencies, i.e. pronouns in Italian and Spanish represent 23% and 26% of the subjects, while in English they cover the majority of the cases (i.e. 63%).

A different picture emerges from the analysis of the distribution of adjectival modifiers across languages, since the three rankings share similar trends. As shown in Figure 5, for all languages *amod* relations appear early in the ranking and then tend to decrease in the second half. While for English they already appear in the first bin, for both Romance languages the first occurrences of *amod* relations are found in the second bin. This difference can be explained by considering that also in this area English is characterized by a generally fixed order or at most slightly variable structures.

5.1.2 Adjectival modifiers: word order analysis

Let us start from the distribution of adjectival modifiers (whose frequency of occurrence is reported in Table 2, Section 3): in English, 97% of *amod* relations are right-headed (i.e. $d < h$, see example 1c), whereas in Italian and Spanish 70% and 72% of the cases respectively represent left-headed DRs (i.e. $h > d$, see examples 1a and 1b).

- (1) a. *Piastrelle in cemento colorato [...]*
 Tiles in cement-NOUN **colored-ADJ** [...]
 ‘Colored cement tiles [...]
- b. *Putin transmitió al titular Cubano [...]*
 Putin transmitted to-the representative-NOUN **Cuban-ADJ** [...]
 ‘Putin transmitted to the Cuban representative [...]
- c. *how could we make it settle in a new house [...]*
 how could we make it settle in a **new-ADJ** house-NOUN [...]

The question which immediately arises is how pre- and post- nominal adjectival modifiers are distributed in the LISCA language-specific rankings. As shown in Figure 6, for English the percentage of pre-nominal adjectives is much higher in all bins than Italian and Spanish; there are only very few cases of post-nominal adjectives which mainly occur in the tail of the LISCA ranking. On the contrary, Italian and Spanish are characterized by an opposite but less sharp distribution: post-nominal adjectives cover the majority of the *amod* relations occurring in the head of the LISCA ranking, which however also contains instances of pre-nominal adjectives.

FIGURE 6. DISTRIBUTION OF PRE- AND POST-NOMINAL ADJECTIVES ACROSS THE LISCA BINS FOR ITALIAN, SPANISH AND ENGLISH.

This follows from the different degree of word order flexibility which characterizes English as opposed to Italian and Spanish. Interestingly, 2a) and 2b) below exemplify pre-nominal adjectives occurring in the head of the Italian and Spanish LISCA rankings. The high score assigned by LISCA to the *amod* relations linking *doppio* ‘double’ and *excesiva* ‘excessive’ to their head cannot be accounted for in terms of frequency only. Even though the pre-nominal word order is less frequent, *amod* DRs in 2a) and 2b) below are classified as unmarked constructions. This fact demonstrates that the language model underlying LISCA is able to discern unmarked from marked constructions on the basis of several interacting factors: word order is one of them, but not the only one. In the Italian example, *a doppio taglio* ‘double edged’ is a fixed multi-word expression (which is introduced by a simple preposition, rather than by an articulated preposition): this fact could have contributed to the classification of this *amod* relation as an unmarked construction.

- (2) a. È un’ arma a doppio taglio
 is a sword with **double-ADJ** cut-NOUN
 ‘It is a double edged sword’
- b. [...] no puede server de excesiva referencia [...]
 [...] not can serve of **excessive-ADJ** reference-NOUN
 ‘[...] it cannot serve as an excessive reference’

Consider now the tail of the LISCA ranked lists of DRs. Interestingly, 40% of the total amount of English post-nominal *amods* occurring in the tail are

represented by cases of adjectives headed by a pronoun (see example 3). The two Romance languages show the same tendency: adjectives headed by pronouns are all placed in the tail of the rankings, regardless of whether they occur pre- or post-nominally. These examples suggest that another property contributes to this LISCA score, namely the grammatical category of the head (pronoun). In fact, it is worth noticing that, while for English such cases show post-pronominal adjectives (which are non-canonical, thus likely to be placed in the ranking tail), in Italian and Spanish adjectives occurring also in canonical positions appear in the tail of the ranking, i.e. they result as marked and atypical.

- (3) *But they haven't been up to anything extraordinary*
But they haven't been up to anything-PRON **extraordinary-ADJ**

Last but not least, it is worth reporting here the length of *amod* DR instances across the languages considered. If on the one hand Italian and Spanish are characterized, on average, by longer *amod* relations with respect to English (5.02 and 6.03 vs 3.55 respectively), on the other hand the three languages share a similar length-based distribution of *amod* relations across the bins: in all cases, the longest links concentrate in the tail of the rankings, with the 10th bin containing links whose length is significantly higher than the average (i.e. 8.50 and 10.17 in Italian and Spanish vs 5.05 in English).

5.1.3 Nominal subjects: word order analysis

Consider now the distribution of nominal subjects in the LISCA ranking for each language. As in the case of *amod*, English vs Italian and Spanish are characterized by a different degree of word order flexibility. As reported in Section 3 (Table 2), the frequency of post-verbal subjects for English is much lower than for Romance languages. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of pre- vs post-verbal subjects across the bins: whereas for English post-verbal subjects mainly occur in the tail of the ranking, for Italian and Spanish all bins combine both of them, although with a different ratio.

FIGURE 7. DISTRIBUTION OF PRE- AND POST-VERBAL SUBJECTS ACROSS THE LISCA BINS FOR ITALIAN, SPANISH AND ENGLISH.

English post-verbal subjects are mainly restricted to parenthetical clauses, as exemplified in 4 below:

- (4) [...] *said Bush* [...] [*...*], *said-VERB Bush-NOUN* [...]

For Italian and Spanish, post-verbal subjects cover instead a variety of cases, exemplified in sentences (5a-d) below, which are ranked in the middle part and the tail of the LISCA ranking. These post-verbal subjects include passive (5c) and interrogative (5d) constructions, a long distance dependency (5b) as well as a topicalized oblique complement in (5a), thus suggesting that several properties, besides word order, are likely to contribute to the low ranking of these relations.

- (5) a. *Dalla rabbia dei valonesi non si salva*
 From-the rage of Valaisers not CLIT save-VERB
niente e nessuno
nothing-NOUN and nobody
 ‘Nothing and no one is saved from the anger of the Valonese’
- b. *Hanno votato per Giorgio Napolitano solo*
 Have voted-VERB for Giorgio Napolitano only
i partiti della maggioranza
 the **parties-NOUN** of-the majority
 ‘Only the majority parties voted for Giorgio Napolitano.’
- c. *Il 6 sarà allestita una*

- The 6th will_be set_up-VERB a
grande libreria
 big **bookshop-NOUN**
 ‘On the 6th a big bookshop will be set up’
- d. *Come si chiama la moglie di Kurt Cobain?*
 How is called-VERB the **wife-NOUN** of Kurt Cobain?
 ‘What’s the name of Kurt Cobain’s wife?’

Similarly, for Spanish, subjects involved in less prototypical, but still allowed, constructions are positioned in the ranking tail (see 6).

- (6) a. *A los que ni tan siquiera les interesó*
 To whom who not even them interest-VERB
la primera película [...]
 the first **movie-NOUN [...]**
 ‘Those who did not even like the first film [...]’
- b. *[...] afirma su hermana*
 [...] affirms-VERB his **sister-NOUN**

Consider now the relationship between *nsubj* dependency length and word order. As in the case of *amod* DRs, longer links concentrate in the tail of the rankings for all languages: in the 10th bin, for instance, the average length of lexical subject relations is 14 tokens for the Romance languages and 10 for English (against an overall average length of 10.48, 10.10 and 7.26 for Italian, Spanish and English respectively). Other interesting properties are worth reporting here on the relationship between *nsubj* length and word order. For all considered languages, longer dependencies are observed with the dominant Subject-Verb order: the average length of right-headed *nsubj* relations is higher than the average length of left-headed ones. In other words, all languages tend to minimize the dependency length when an alternative marked (with respect to the dominant, i.e. most frequent one) word order is used. Besides this general trend, dependency length minimization varies across languages: whereas in English the average dependency length of post-verbal subjects is only slightly lower with respect to pre-verbal ones (i.e. 2.9 vs 3.8), for Italian and Spanish length minimization is more evident (i.e. 3.49 vs 5.50 and 3.21 vs 5.29 respectively).

A last remark is in order here: namely, Spanish turned out to be the only language with a high proportion (24%) of post-verbal subjects ranked in the 4th LISCA bin (namely the first bin of *nsubj* appearance). After inspecting the type of sentences where they occur, we found out that they are mainly constituted by parenthetical clauses (see sentence 6b) possibly occurring in reported speech. Although the proposed methodology turned out to be able to capture different shades of markedness of language constructions, this result reported

for Spanish highlights one possible drawback of the proposed analysis methodology. The multilingual approach, which compares the distribution of DRs in different treebanks, can provide misleading results if different textual genres or language varieties are included in the considered target treebanks. In other words, it could be the case that part of the observed differences in DR ranking originates in the texts constituting the treebank rather than in the language. In order to address this potential problem, Alzetta et al. (2019) proposed a cross-lingual analysis approach, which ensures the comparability of the DR multilingual rankings: the results of the cross-lingual analysis of the distribution of *amod* and *nsubj* DRs across the language-specific LISCA rankings are reported below.

5.2 Cross-lingual Results

The cross-lingual analysis approach is exemplified here on the ISTD section of the Italian Universal Dependencies treebank: typological differences and similarities are acquired comparing the LISCA rankings of the Italian treebank obtained using three different language models, i.e. LISCA-LM_{Ita}, LISCA-LM_{Esp} and LISCA-LM_{Eng}. By comparing the ranking obtained with the LISCA-LM for the same language (i.e. LISCA-LM_{Ita}, henceforth referred to as *mono-lingual ranking*) with the ranking obtained on the basis of the LM for another language (in the case at hand, LISCA-LM_{Esp} and LISCA-LM_{Eng}, henceforth referred to as *cross-lingual rankings*), the distance of languages with respect to specific properties can be measured. The intuition underlying this type of analysis is that the positions of the same DR instance in the three rankings can be used to investigate typological features of the involved languages without possible interferences due to the composition of the target treebank. This approach to the study of typological features is reminiscent of the typological approach to acquisitional studies, where typological trends are used to explain various aspects of second language acquisition (see e.g. Giacalone Ramat, 2003). In other words, the cross-lingual rankings obtained with LMs for other languages can be seen as a way to model the subtle and complex role of the source language (L1, corresponding to the other language) on the acquisition of a second language (L2, i.e. the language we are currently focusing on, Italian in the case at hand).

The comparison of mono-lingual vs cross-lingual rankings of the same set of DR instances has been carried out by focusing on two main aspects: *i*) the movement of the DR instance and its direction (up or down in the cross-lingual rankings with respect to the monolingual one), and *ii*) the “stride” length, i.e. the number of gained or lost positions going up or down in the cross-lingual ranking. We refer to these aspects as *DR fluctuations*: given the complex in-

terplay of factors underlying the positioning of a given DR in the LISCA ranking, we believe that DR fluctuations can be used to “measure” the typological distance of languages. As in the multilingual analysis, we will focus on the distribution of *amod* and *nsubj* relations across the rankings obtained with the different LISCA language-specific models, with a specific focus on DR fluctuations.

5.2.1 Adjectival modifiers: cross-lingual analysis

Let us first consider the fluctuations of ISDT *amod* relations observed in the cross-lingual rankings.

FIGURE 8. DISTRIBUTION OF ISDT PRE- AND POST-NOMINAL AMODS FLUCTUATING UP OR DOWN IN THE CROSS-LINGUAL RANKINGS WITH RESPECT TO THE MONOLINGUAL ONE.

	Pre-nominal adjectives		Post-nominal adjectives	
	Going Up	Going Down	Going Up	Going Down
LISCA-LM _{Eng}	21,691.18 (7.52%)	2,566.57 (0.89%)	290.13 (0.10%)	40,934.52 (14.20%)
LISCA-LM _{Esp}	1,541.31 (0.53%)	9,163.83 (3.17%)	5,462.83 (1.89%)	5,322.66 (1.84%)

TABLE 3. AVG AND PERCENTAGE DIFFERENCE OF RANKING POSITIONS OF PRE- AND POST-NOMINAL AMOD IN CROSS-LINGUAL RANKINGS WITH RESPECT TO THE MONOLINGUAL ONE.

Figure 8 and Table 3 document observed DR fluctuations from complementary perspectives, in particular: Figure 8 reports the percentage distribu-

tion of fluctuating DR instances classified on the basis of the movement direction observed in the cross-lingual rankings (obtained with LISCA-LM_{Esp} and LISCA-LM_{Eng}) with respect to the monolingual ranking obtained using the LISCA-LM_{Ita}; Table 3 details the average number of positions covered by each movement, by distinguishing between pre- and post-nominal adjectival modifiers. As it can be seen, in the ranking obtained using the English language model the percentage of pre-nominal adjectival modifiers going up in the ranking with respect to their position in the monolingual ranking (i.e. obtained using the LISCA-LM_{Ita}) is higher (86.50%) than the percentage of DR fluctuations recorded with the Spanish model (28.63%). This follows from the fact that right-headed adjectives are more prototypical in English than in Italian: as a consequence, they are assigned higher scores by LISCA and are moved up in the ranking. On the contrary, recorded differences concerning *amod* dependency direction between the two Romance languages are less sharp.

Data reported in Figure 8 are not sufficient, alone, to fully account for language differences: we also need to consider the “stride” length, i.e. the extension of each observed movement expressed in terms of intervening positions between the original (in the monolingual ranking) and the target (in the cross-lingual ranking). In Table 3, it is interesting to note that in the ranking obtained with the LISCA-LM_{Eng} the average movement length of pre-nominal adjectives going up in the ranked list is significantly high (i.e. 21,691.18 positions, corresponding to 7.52% of the ranking length); on the other hand, post-nominal adjectives go down in the ranked list, with a highly significant difference, namely the average movement length is almost doubled (40,934.52, covering 14.20% of ranked DR list). The ranking obtained with the LISCA-LM_{Esp} is much closer to the monolingual ranking: pre-nominal adjectives, whose frequency of use is slightly lower with respect to Italian, move down (with an average movement length of 9,163.83), whereas post-nominal ones are almost stable (the movement length is much shorter and approximately the same in both directions).

These results can be easily explained with the lower degree of prototypicality of left-headed adjectives in English with respect to Italian and also Spanish. As proof, consider the examples in (7), with post-nominal (7a) and pre-nominal (7b) adjectives. The *amod* relation linking *ultimo* ‘last’ to its head in (7b) is placed in position 100,501 and 103,937 in the LISCA-LM_{Ita} and LISCA-LM_{Esp} ranked lists respectively, but raises to position 72,378 in the LISCA-LM_{Eng} ranking. The reverse occurs with the *amod* relation linking the adjective *russo* ‘russian’ to its head in (7a), that goes down about 47,000 positions in the LISCA-LM_{Eng} ranking.

- (7) a. [...] *i soldati dell’ esercito russo sono arrivati*
 [...] the soldiers of-the army-NOUN **russian-ADJ** are arrived

- ‘[...] russian army soldiers arrived’
 b. *E soltanto nell’ ultimo interrogatorio*
 And only in-the **last-ADJ** interrogation-NOUN
davanti al PM [...]
 in-front-of PM [...]
 ‘And only during the last interrogation in front of the PM [...]’

5.2.2 Nominal subjects: cross-lingual analysis

Similar results are reported for nominal subjects, as detailed in Figure 9 and Table 4.

FIGURE 9. DISTRIBUTION OF PRE- VS POST-VERBAL LEXICAL SUBJECTS FLUCTUATING UP OR DOWN IN THE CROSS-LINGUAL RANKINGS WITH RESPECT TO MONOLINGUAL ONE.

	Pre-verbal subjects		Post-verbal subjects	
	Going Up	Going Down	Going Up	Going Down
LISCA-LM _{Eng}	17,193.19 (5.96%)	199.15 (0.06%)	1,429.61 (0.49%)	10,710.80 (3.71%)
LISCA-LM _{Esp}	8,648.32 (2.99%)	165.38 (0.04%)	9,283.76 (3.21%)	463.59 (0.16%)

TABLE 4. AVG AND PERCENTAGE DIFFERENCE OF RANKING POSITIONS OF PRE- AND POST-VERBAL NSUBJ IN THE CROSS-LINGUAL RANKINGS WITH RESPECT TO THE MONOLINGUAL ONE.

In the LISCA-LM_{Eng} ranking, 92.57% of pre-verbal subjects are raised, with each movement covering 17,193.19 positions on average. This result, in line with our expectations based on the results of the multilingual analysis (see Section 4.1), can be seen as following from the canonical position of subjects

in English: given that Italian and Spanish are pro-drop languages, while English is not, the three LMs demonstrate to account for subjects in different ways, i.e. the LISCA-LM_{Eng} assigns higher scores on average. Nevertheless, the linguistic context of the subject still plays a crucial role when computing the LISCA score. Consider the examples in (8): although they both contain pre-verbal subjects, while *cosa* ‘thing’ in (8a) drops in the ranking obtained with LISCA-LM_{Eng}, *nuvole* ‘clouds’ in (8b) raises. The lack of determiner in (8b) is more typical for English nouns rather than for Italian and Spanish ones, thus causing all nominal subjects of this kind to raise in the ranking obtained with LISCA-LM_{Eng}.

- (8) a. *E la cosa importante è che [...]*
 And the **thing-SUBJ** important is-VERB that [...]
 ‘And the important thing is that [...]’
- b. *Nuvole vagano tra queste rocce [...]*
Clouds-SUBJ wander-VERB between these rocks [...]
 ‘Clouds wander around these rocks [...]’

Consider now the LISCA-LM_{Esp} ranking. In Figure 9 it can be observed that, as in the case of the English model, the majority of pre-verbal subjects rise in the ranking, but with a main difference, i.e. the movement involves a limited number of positions (i.e. 8,648.32 on average, almost half of the positions with respect to English), showing that the Spanish LM is more aligned with respect to Italian than English.

For what concerns post-verbal subjects, it can be observed that with the LISCA-LM_{Eng} the majority of them (80.28%) drops in the ranking, although the number of lost positions is not particularly high (10,710.80 on average). This is the case, for instance, of the sentences in (9) containing *nsubj* DRs which go down in the LISCA-LM_{Eng} ranking and move up in the LISCA-LM_{Esp}. This can be seen as following from the fact that both Italian and Spanish allow for left-headed subjects (whose frequency of use is 22.38% and 16.94% of the cases respectively), more than English where they represent exceptional and very rarely occurring cases (with a relative frequency of 3.58%).

- (9) a. *In che cosa sfocia il fiume Cubango ?*
 In what thing flows-VERB the **river-SUBJ** Cubango ?
 ‘What does the Cubango River flow into?’
- b. *Sulle questioni di metodo, inoltre,*
 On-the questions of method, moreover,
sembra tramontata l’ idea di [...]
 seems-VERB faded the **idea-SUBJ** of [...]
 ‘On the questions of method, moreover, the idea of [...] seems to have faded’

- c. *L' occasione propizia gliel' ha offerta*
 The opportunity favourable to-her it has offered-VERB
Alija Izetbegovic [...]
Alija Izetbegovic-SUBJ [...]
 'Alija Izetbegovic offered her a favourable opportunity [...]

5.3 Summary and Contribution

The results obtained through the multilingual and cross-lingual analyses turned out to provide convergent and at the same time complementary perspectives on the topic of word order variation in VERB-SUBJ and NOUN-ADJ constructions.

Consider first the VERB-SUBJ construction. From both analyses, similar language-specific properties emerged. For all three languages the Subject-Verb order is the unmarked one, with a main difference: Romance languages on the one hand and English on the other hand are characterized by a different degree of word order flexibility, as testified by the much higher percentage of post-verbal subjects in Italian and Spanish with respect to English. This general picture is enriched by the results of the multi-lingual analysis, which include both language-specific and general trends, as reported below:

- English post-verbal subjects are classified as highly marked constructions, being concentrated in the tail of the LISCA ranking, whereas all Italian and Spanish LISCA bins combine both pre- and post-verbal subjects, although with a different ratio (the frequency of Verb-Subject occurrences is much higher in the tail of the ranking);
- post-verbal subjects occur in highly restricted contexts of occurrence in all languages: in English post-verbal subjects are attested in parenthetical clauses only, in Italian and Spanish they cover instead a variety of cases including passive and interrogative constructions;
- an interesting interaction with the grammatical category of the subject (noun vs pronoun) emerged: for all languages, pronominal subjects concentrate in the first bins (in Italian and Spanish, regardless of the order with respect to the verb);
- another interesting relationship emerged between *nsubj* dependency length and word order:
 - for the three languages, longer links concentrate in the tail of the ranking (English exhibits shorter links with respect to Italian and Spanish);
 - for all considered languages, longer dependencies are observed with the dominant Subject-Verb order, whereas dependency length tends to be minimized when an alternative marked word

- order is used;
- besides this general trend, dependency length minimization varies across languages: whereas in English the average dependency length of post-verbal subjects is only slightly lower with respect to pre-verbal ones, for Italian and Spanish length minimization is more evident.

Last but not least, cross-lingual analysis results quantify the pairwise distance between languages for what concerns the distribution of pre- and post-verbal subjects. In the ranking obtained with LISCA-LM_{Eng}, a polarization of the *nsubj* positions is observed, with an increased distance between pre- and post-verbal subjects: namely, 92.57% of pre-verbal subjects are raised, with each movement covering 17,193.19 positions on average, and 80.28% of post-verbal ones go down but with shorter movements. As expected, LISCA-LM_{Esp} turned out to be more aligned with Italian than English: both pre- and post-verbal subjects raise in the ranking but with much shorter movements.

Similar considerations apply to the NOUN-ADJ construction, which is characterized by different degrees of word order flexibility: in Italian and Spanish post-nominal adjectival constructions represent the unmarked case, whereas pre-nominal adjectives are the almost exclusive order for English. From the multilingual analysis both language-specific and general trends emerged, as detailed below:

- in English pre-nominal adjectives are distributed almost exclusively in all bins, with only very few cases of post-nominal adjectives which are classified as highly marked constructions (mainly occurring in the tail of the LISCA ranking). In Italian and Spanish, all bins (except the first Spanish one) combine post-nominal adjectives (which, corresponding to the unmarked order, represent the majority of the cases) with pre-nominal ones, showing a higher word order flexibility;
- an interesting interaction with the grammatical category of the head (noun vs pronoun) emerged: for all languages, adjectives headed by pronouns concentrate in the tail of the LISCA ranking, even when used in the dominant order;
- a marked word order used within a fixed multi-word expression appears in the head of the ranking (i.e. it is classified as unmarked), suggesting an interesting interaction between word order markedness and fixed expressions;
- another interesting relationship emerged between *amod* dependency length and word order: Italian and Spanish are characterized, on average, by longer *amod* relations with respect to English. All languages however share a similar length-based distribution of *amod* relations across the bins, with the longest links concentrating in the tail of the rankings.

The results emerging from the cross-lingual analysis are in line with what observed for *nsubj*. The English ranking shows a polarization of positions, with pre-nominal adjectives going up and post-nominal ones going down, with a main difference with respect to *nsubj*, i.e. the stride length which ranges between 21,691.18 (up) and 40,934.52 (down) positions. This difference can be seen as resulting from the fact that, contrary to the *nsubj* case, English vs Italian and Spanish are characterized by different unmarked orders, namely Adjective-Noun vs Noun-Adjective. On the other hand, the ranking obtained with LISCA-LM_{Exp} is much closer to the monolingual Italian ranking.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a novel methodology aimed at meeting the newly defined needs of Distributional Typology by extracting qualitative and quantitative information about a wide range of fine-grained features from “gold” dependency treebanks for different languages. The method has been tested in a case study on word order patterns carried out on UD treebanks for three languages (Italian, English and Spanish): in particular, we focused on the analysis of VERB-SUBJ and NOUN-ADJ constructions taken as representative of the clausal and phrasal levels respectively. Going back to the research questions we started with, on the basis of achieved results we can provide a twofold answer.

From a methodological point of view (RQ1), we showed that the devised NLP-based method is able to go beyond simple frequency-based accounts of individual properties and to extract local and global characteristics of the “linguistic environment” in which dependency relation instances occur. By relying on a language model which encodes a wide range of language features, it has been possible to infer quantitative evidence about the gradual transition from unmarked (or prototypical) to marked (or less canonical) word order patterns. Such transition has been analysed from a twofold perspective, namely multilingual and cross-lingual. Interestingly, the general trends identified with the two types of analysis are similar but with a main methodological difference. The cross-lingual analysis proved to be effective in overcoming well-known disadvantages of corpus-based typological studies, namely the risk of accounting for characteristics of the corpus rather than of real language usage.

From a linguistic point of view (RQ2), by relying on a wide range of properties aimed at defining and weighting the markedness degree of a given DR, it has been possible to reconstruct an articulated profile of word order patterns associated with specific constructions in the languages taken into account, which is in line with the literature on the topic and which has been enriched with new insightful evidence. The fine-grained variables which have been

monitored range from dependency direction and length, to morpho-syntactic properties (e.g. grammatical category) to other contextual features (e.g. occurrence in passive or impersonal constructions). These properties have been investigated with a specific view to their impact and role in influencing the preference towards one order or the other. For instance, in the VERB-SUBJ construction dependency length minimization turned out to vary significantly according to whether a dominant or marked order is used: to our knowledge, this represents novel and original evidence which enriches the already complex and articulated picture of word order variation in the VERB-SUBJ construction.

The computational treebank-based approaches proposed in this paper for the study of word order patterns also open a lot of interesting possibilities for future research. Among them, it is worth mentioning here the application of the methodology to other languages, including typologically distant ones, and the analysis of other dependency relations as well as of more complex structures such as dependency subtrees.

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